

İslam Şehri Kavramının Temelleri ve Modern Şehircilik Modelleriyle Karşılaştırılması ¹

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Özet

Bu çalışma, modern şehrin işlevsel mantığı ile geleneksel İslam şehrinin medeniyet-merkezli ruhu arasındaki köklü ayrımı, köken ve sosyo-mekânsal boyutlarıyla bir değerlendirme konusu yapmaktadır. Karşılaştırmalı kuramsal bir analiz ve literatür taraması zemininde yürütülen araştırma, bu iki modelin yalnızca biçimsel olarak ayırmadığı aksine insan, toplum ve mekân arasındaki ilişkiyi tanımlayan iki zıt paradigmaya dayandığı hipotezini merkeze alır. Araştırma, sermaye birikimini önceleyen modern şehrin, bireyi topluma yabancılaştıran, mekânı metalaştıran ve tarihsel hafızayı aşındıran bir yörünge izlediğini ortaya koymaktadır. Bunun karşısında konumlanan İslam şehri ise, bir 'anlam coğrafyası' olarak belirir; beraberlik ruhu, insan ölçeği ve manevi bir merkez etrafında örülen dokusuyla, aidiyet ve bütünlük üreten bir model sunmaktadır. Bu itibarla çalışma, modern şehirleşmenin doğurduğu krizlere yönelik eleştirel bir bakış açısı geliştirirken, yitirilmiş bir denge arayışında olan günümüz şehirciliği için geleneksel paradigmalardan barındırdığı ilham verici potansiyele işaret etmektedir.

Fundamentals of the Islamic City Concept and Comparison with Modern Urbanism Models

Keywords:

Islamic City, Western City, Modernism, Postmodernism, Civilization.

Abstract

This study investigates the fundamental distinction between the functional logic of the modern city and the civilization-centered spirit of the traditional Islamic city, with its origins and socio-spatial dimensions. The research, which is conducted on the basis of a comparative theoretical analysis and literature review, centers on the hypothesis that these two models are not only formally distinct, but on the contrary, they are based on two opposing ontological paradigms defining the relationship between humans, society and space. The research reveals that the modern city, which prioritizes capital accumulation, follows a trajectory that alienates the individual from society, commodifies space and erodes historical memory. Positioned against this, the Islamic city emerges as a 'geography of meaning'; with its spirit of togetherness, human scale and texture woven around a spiritual center, it offers a model that produces belonging and integrity. In this respect, the study develops a critical perspective on the ontological crises caused by modern urbanization, while pointing to the inspiring potential of traditional paradigms for today's urbanism in search of a lost balance.

¹ This article has been derived from the doctoral dissertation titled "Urbanization and transformation of Islamic cities in Türkiye: Models of Eastern and Southeastern Anatolia".

1. INTRODUCTION

Space is a raw material upon which civilizations stamp their seal; the city is the most intricate and legible form of this seal. A society's worldview, its understanding of justice, and its relationship with spirituality find their most concrete expression in the architectural language and the spiritual geography of the city. In this context, the city is a reflection of the civilization that built it; indeed, as Huntington (2015: 45) noted, great civilizations throughout history have defined themselves through great religions. The spatial order of traditional societies, through Ferdinand Tönnies's classic conceptualization, reflects a societal spirit where individuals are bound together by common beliefs, traditions, and intimate relationships (Tönnies, 1987). In this structure, the city is not merely a settlement, but a living organism where a collective memory and a moral order are shared.

However, the historical rupture experienced in the West, particularly after the Industrial Revolution, fundamentally shook this organic relationship. As will be emphasized throughout this text, with the centering of capitalism's profit motive (Keleş, 1976) and the rational spirit described by Weber (1997), the very ontology of the city underwent a transformation. This new paradigm is the spatial equivalent of the modern societal structure that Tönnies defined as *Gesellschaft* (society), where relationships are impersonal, rational, and contractual. As Wirth (1938) pointed out, the density and heterogeneity of the modern metropolis weakened traditional bonds, anonymized the individual, and reduced space to a sum of functional units. This is no longer a "city" but rather "the urban", operating on the logic of modernist planning and capital accumulation.

This study takes this conceptual and historical distinction as its starting point, subjecting the modern Western urban model and the traditional Islamic city concept to a comparative analysis-not merely as two different morphologies, but as two irreducible existential paradigms. The main hypothesis of the research is that the fundamental differences in how these two models position the human being, society, and nature play a key role in understanding the many urban, social, and ecological crises of today, from Lefebvre's (2018) discussions on the right to the city to Jacobs's (1961) critique of modernist planning.

To establish this hypothesis, first, the relationship of the Western metropolis with capitalism and modernism will be examined in depth; then, in light of the works of researchers such as AlSayyad (1991) and Lapidus (1984), the foundational principles, social organization models, and spatial identity of the Islamic city will be set forth. Ultimately, by conducting a comprehensive comparison of these two paradigms, a critical discussion will be held on the crisis facing today's urban spheres, and it will be questioned what lessons can be drawn for more just and sustainable urban futures.

2. CITIES ACCORDING TO THEIR BELIEFS

In city systems, sacred values and the spaces that develop accordingly come to the forefront based on the form of belief. This section, focusing on religions and civilizations, addresses the places of worship that have been seen as the centers of civilizations and cities throughout history. Indeed, cities have developed around these centers. As Huntington (2015:45) points out, the major civilizations in human history have been significantly identified with the world's great religions.

Similar to Huntington, Mumford (1987), who accepts that religion is influential upon the city, states that cities began to form as the king incorporated religious powers, and emphasizes that religion was as influential as the economy in the development of cities. However, in the West, following the increasingly felt impact of capitalism and modernism, the influence of religion and economy in cities gradually gave way to the economy, and the effect of religion on cities diminished. Consequently, whether a city is based on religion or economy not only brings about differentiation in urban spaces, but there can also be differences among cities originating from the same foundation.² However, generally speaking, in cities shaped by forms of belief, high and domed structures are prominent, likely due to the inherent human need for shelter and security.

One of the first examples that can be given in this context is the Egyptian pyramids, whose construction secrets are still debated today. In 3000 B.C., Egypt was under the influence of a polytheistic religion. In Egypt, everything was centered around the palace of the Pharaoh, who was seen as a god-king. It was believed that the

² In this context, there is a fundamental difference between Islamic Cities and Western cities. To give an example, while in the intellectual foundation of the Islamic religion it is believed that life after death will continue in another realm, in the Western belief system, life after death will continue again in this world, and space will become permanent. The statement in Hobbes's work, "God's kingdom is to be on earth; when the Messiah returns, it will come down from heaven to God's people; people will not go up to it from earth" (2007: 312), explains the Western belief system.

Pharaoh himself was immortal and could grant immortality to others, and that defying him would end one's afterlife (Neill & Hardy, 2002: 54- 55). Egyptian city architecture depicts the beliefs of the period. The city tombs were created with beliefs in inviolability, durability, courage, wealth, and the protection of treasure (Mutlu, 2001). The pyramids, with their solid forms, are symbols of eternity. The closed nature of the pyramid form is an indicator of the belief in human sublimity and immortality. The unadorned halls and rooms, while suggesting silence, evoke a sense of infinity (Turani, 2010: 43-75). Another example with a similar form to the Egyptian pyramids but with more external detail is Mesopotamian architecture. In Mesopotamian myths, it is told that the gods created humans to supply the food, clothing, and other needs of the fully equipped temple. Thus, the god would not have to worry about production (Neill, 2002: 35).

The Greeks, as Mutlu (2001) emphasizes, worshipped gods in human form and built chambered temples to house the statues, belongings, and sacred animals of the gods. A similar temple form is also seen in Rome.

At the front of Roman temples, there was an area for the public to gather, where speeches on religious or political topics were delivered to the people (Mutlu, 2001). The columns in the temples here are also noteworthy. In Mayan temples, contrary to the columns seen in Ancient Greece and Rome, a form that tapers from bottom to top, as in Egyptian and Mesopotamian architecture, is observed. The Mayans developed an accurate calendar and a form of writing. Only a part of this writing system has been deciphered today. While it is clear that the society was ruled by priests, the nature of the power that enabled the inclusion of the inhabitants in the construction of the great temples has not yet been revealed (Neill, 2002: 440). A form similar to the chambered and slightly domed structure at the top of Mayan temples is also found in Buddhist cities.

The most visible effect of Buddhism in the city and in architecture is the dome-shaped stupa. While the dome in the stupa is believed to protect the world, these dome-shaped stupas have taken on the form of a tower over time (Çakıroğlu & Engin, 2014: 78). The combination of the dome and the tower is an indicator of how much importance people gave to protection. While there are similarities among the examples given so far, there is a difference in the reflection of the Jainist understanding on the city, both in the material used in construction and in appearance. The prevailing thought is that this difference may stem from the abundance of marble stone in the region.

In Jainism, because love, compassion, and non-violence are at the forefront, the temples in the city were built of white marble (Çakıroğlu & Engin, 2014: 79). The prayer of the Jainists, whose beliefs founded on tolerance are reflected in their architecture, is as follows: "I forgive all living beings in the world, and may all living beings forgive me. Everything in this world is my friend and companion. I have no enemy" (Batuk, t.y.).

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In the city temple architecture of Taoism (6th century B.C.), which is similar to Mesopotamian and Buddhist temples, square and circle shapes are dominant. The square represents the earth, while the circle represents heaven. The temple is the point where the earth and heaven unite. For this reason, squares and circles are overlapped (Çakıroğlu & Engin, 2014: 82). Structures that can be considered a mixture of Taoist temples and Roman temples, where squares and circles coexist, began to be seen in cities with the Jewish faith.

Judaism is a monotheistic religion based on the belief in an afterlife, with the Torah as its holy book. The Jewish place of worship is called a synagogue, and synagogues function in cities as houses of prayer, assembly, community, and education. Synagogues also contain a courtyard, a fountain, and a dining hall. The place considered sacred within the synagogue is the Heikhal (Ark). The Heikhal is a cabinet or niche located on the wall of the synagogue that faces Jerusalem (Türkoğlu, 2003). Another structure similar to the synagogue is the Cathedral, which is the reflection of Christianity in the city.

The influence of belief is also seen in the architecture created by Christianity, a divinely revealed religion. This belief contributed the church, the martyrion (shrine for a martyr), and the baptistery to architecture (Mutlu, 2001). Upon entering a church, one walks towards the apse; this path signifies the path to Jesus (Turani, 2010: 453-454). While a situation of sanctification is present through this depiction, in mosques, which are the reflection of Islam in cities, no single element of the mosque is sanctified.

The elements of the mosque, which forms the center of Islamic cities, are the dome, mihrab, minbar, and minaret. The dome, with its effect of a mysterious void, lends a sacred atmosphere while also indicating the center where attention is focused (Keleş et al., 2001: 9). The mihrab, a niche set into a wall, indicates the direction of the qibla, which is the direction of Mecca; the minbar serves as the pulpit from which the sermon is delivered on Fridays, and the minaret plays a role in calling the faithful to prayer (Grabar, 1998: 106-122).

In conclusion, it can be said that in the classical period, every society expressed its own worldview through the socio-spatial element of the temple and the place of worship. After the classical period, in which religion was influential, capitalism became effective over cities.

3. CONCEPTION OF CITY IN THE MODERN AND POST-MODERN WORLD

This section discusses the effects of capitalism and its tools, modernism and post-modernism, on cities.

3.1. Capitalist Urban Model

Since the process of capitalism, which began with the Industrial Revolution, first emerged in the geography inhabited by Western civilization, the foundation of the Western concept of the city was also laid during this process. This point does not mean that capitalism only affected the West. While capitalism formed the foundations of the Western City, it has influenced almost all world cities through its expansionist policy.

Capitalism is an economic system in which individuals own all factors of production and the profit motive constitutes the fundamental guide for all types of production activities (Keleş, 1976). This economic system regards “earning” as the purpose of human life. Earning is an open and absolute fundamental principle of capitalism. Those who do not act in accordance with the principles of capitalism are pushed out of the system. This situation is likened to a worker who does not or does not want to obey the rules being thrown onto the street (Weber, 1997: 49). The main characteristic of the system is the freedom to buy and sell with a competitive motive for individual units within an economic environment governed by the formation of free prices and the principle of profit maximization (Keleş, 1976, 29-30).

Capitalism, which takes economic life under its control, educates employers and workers, whom it accepts as economic subjects, and then subjects them to a selection based on their economic resilience. This act of selection occurs through adaptation to the characteristics of capitalism. A way of life and a professional ethic are considered to have won the victory if they adapt well to the characteristics of capitalism and are adopted not just by single individuals, but by groups (Weber, 1997: 49). This situation depicted by Weber from the capitalist system has many reflections in society. For, while the capitalist system brings forth a completely new social order, capitalism positions itself outside of all existing habits and life experiences. The reflection of the new social order brought by this system can be read through its cities.

Today, in the structure of cities, which are an area of exploitation for capitalism (Harvey, 2013: 131), class differentiations are seen as a result of the capitalist system. Poor, middle-class, and wealthy neighborhoods are separated from each other by sharp, defined lines (Chapin, 1965: 10-21). The situation of exclusion from the economic system for those who do not adopt capitalist principles also brings with it exclusion in cities. Indeed, the places where low, middle, and high-income groups live within the city vary. The reasons for this situation are income inequality, which leads to economy-based social stratification in society, and imbalances between cities and regions. In capitalist countries where the state does not interfere in social and economic life, not only the growth of cities but also the development of underdeveloped regions is left to the functioning of market forces. In these countries, interregional imbalances are seen as a normal feature of the development process. This is because, as Myrdal also stated, the market mechanism leads to the concentration of the most efficient economic activities in certain settlement centers and the development of a system consisting of wealthy and poor regions within the country. This tendency, which exacerbates inequalities between regions, is a self-reinforcing process that gains strength over time and appears as a function of poverty. Interregional imbalances are expected to be greater in poor countries. Myrdal is of the opinion that these inequalities delay development and integration on a national scale (Keleş, 1976: 31).

In industrialized Western countries, urbanization, as a historical process, is parallel to the Industrial Revolution. When England, Germany, and France reached the urbanization levels that developing countries have reached today, they were much more industrialized nations. However, the urbanization model of capitalist societies is generally disorderly, unplanned, and uncontrolled. Since economic and social development is not tied to a plan in these countries, there is no possibility of bringing urbanization under control within the framework of a development plan. As a result of this, one or a few cities in the country grow disproportionately compared to other cities. That is why countries like England and France have had to resort to measures to limit the growth of cities like London and Paris. The concept of optimal city size is a concept put forward by the planners and economists of these countries as a solution to prevent the excessive growth of cities (Richardson, 1973; as cited in Böventer, 1973, in Keleş, 1976: 30).

According to Mills, capitalism is not the source of the imbalances seen between cities and regions of various sizes. In contrast, according to Castells, capitalist societies are more concerned with the growth of income than with its distribution among social classes and geographical regions. For this reason, the development of income distribution in cities in a way that creates greater inequalities and injustices is not seen as important. Therefore, it is common for the distribution of income or welfare between cities, within cities, and between regions to create greater inequalities and injustices in these societies. If this trend cannot be stopped, social conflicts will

be seen within the city system (Mills, 1974; Castells, 1972, as cited in Keleş, 1976: 31). In modern capitalist society, in addition to the complex market system, the increase in the division of labor, by including the majority of people in this system, could provide social integration, but on the other hand, due to those who cannot be included in the system and the inequalities, it can also cause disruptive effects on social integrity and solidarity (Habermas, 2001: 545-547). According to Harvey, the reason for this entire pessimistic picture is the fact that capitalism needs cities

Capitalism requires urbanization to absorb the surplus product it continuously generates. Thus, an intrinsic link emerges between the development of capitalism and urbanization. Therefore, it should not be considered surprising that there is a great degree of parallelism between the growth graph of capitalist production over time and the one traced by the urbanization of the world's population (Harvey, 2013: 45).

Capitalism's surplus value is the difference between the value produced by the laborer and the income they receive. Capital accumulation is secured through this difference (Marx, 2003: 172-183). Urbanization ensures the absorption of this explained surplus product. This quality of urbanization makes the metropolis indispensable for capitalism. As Harvey (2013) states, there are historical examples of this situation. For instance, Haussmann implemented reforms in Paris geared towards the principles of capitalism. The reforms in the city were carried out with a focus on demolition (Çelik, 2009). Buildings on narrow streets were demolished, roads and avenues were widened, parks and gardens were arranged, and new buildings were constructed (Hasol, 1997). Here, a modern urban concept and an authoritarian approach were displayed (2009). Violence is necessary to build a new world in the city upon the ruins of the old. While the old poor neighborhoods of Paris were being demolished, the power of expropriation was supposedly used for the public good. The reason given for the destruction in the name of public good was carried out for the sake of civilization, environmental improvement, and urban renewal. The real purpose here was to preempt the threat the city posed to public order, public health, and of course, political power, by removing the majority of the working class and other insurgents, along with unsanitary industries, from the Paris city center (Harvey, 2013: 58)

In the context expressed, while the city was being transformed in Paris, some of the city dwellers' houses were subject to demolition. The city dwellers were also thrown out of their houses. Therefore, shantytowns started to form on the outskirts of the city (Çelik, 2009). As explained, Haussmann's urban transformation plan made class differences apparent.

As a result of this policy, when Haussmann faced backlash, he defended himself by saying, "Yes, we demolished many houses, but we built just as many." In Haussmann's plan, cities are seen as machines (Çelik, 2009). The matter described is the phenomenon of absorbing surplus capital through urban transformation³. The successive phases of urban renewal, through the method of "creative destruction" almost always exhibit a class dimension, as it is most often the poor, the deprived, and those marginalized by the political power who are the first and most affected by the process (Harvey, 2013: 58). However, the urban transformation process, initiated to address the problems that arose as a result of the rapid increase in urban populations, unplanned urbanization, and urban renewal, has rapidly advanced industrialization (Yılmaz, 2019). In other words, this tool also strengthens capitalism.

A process similar to the one in Paris took place in New York during the era of Moses. The event that occurred on a global scale, and therefore affected global metropolises, was the pre-2008 capital accumulation in the real estate market (Harvey, 2013: 49). Harvey expresses the event's connection with urbanization as follows:

Until 2008, the prevailing belief in the US was that the real estate market was an important element of economic stability; the crash in the high-tech sector at the end of the 1990s had reinforced this belief. The real estate market was directly absorbing a large portion of surplus capital through new construction (both residential development in city centers and suburbs, and new commercial properties). On the other hand, the rapid increase in housing prices, supported by a reckless wave of mortgages based on historically

³ Urban renewal applications are projects and programs implemented for transformation for reasons such as the revitalization of urban centers, the restoration of fading neighborhood culture, and the restructuring of historical fabrics. In this process, sometimes a local government creates the urban plan and assumes the transformation will be realized by market forces according to the plan; at other times, it carries out a few pioneering construction activities; and at still other times, it merely provides the appropriate infrastructure. See Mayer, 1995; Üstündağ, 2013: 19.

unprecedented low-interest rates, was boosting the consumption of goods and services in the US domestic market. ...

Meanwhile, the process of urbanization also underwent a new scalar transformation, meaning it acquired a global dimension. Therefore, it would be wrong to focus solely on the US here. In Great Britain, Ireland, Spain, and many other countries, the boom in the real estate market, in ways largely parallel to that in the US, constituted the driving force of capitalist dynamics (Harvey, 2013: 52- 54).

Harvey, explaining the housing crisis in the US in the context of urbanization, states that the foundations of the crisis were laid as a result of construction absorbing capitalism's surplus value and banks supporting home purchases with low-interest rates. However, this situation was not only seen in the US but also in Great Britain, Ireland, and Spain.

China's urbanization, ..., followed an extremely different course. The process, in which infrastructure investments took the largest share, immediately gained incredible speed after a brief downturn in 1997. In the last twenty years, the population of more than a hundred cities has exceeded the one million mark; some small cities, like Shenzhen, have transformed into giant metropolises with populations ranging from 6 to 10 million. Industrialization, initially concentrated only in special economic zones, later spread to every municipality willing to absorb surplus capital from abroad and ready to use the resulting profits for rapid growth again. Massive infrastructure projects like dams and highways, all financed by debt, continue to transform the country's landscape. Giant shopping malls, science parks, airports, container ports, all sorts of venues for pleasure and leisure, a wide variety of newly invented cultural institutions, as well as gated residential communities complete with golf courses, etc.-all these stand out in clusters within China's urban landscape, amidst the overcrowded "dormitory towns" located in poor rural areas that serve as a vast labor source to which workers from more central workplaces return at the end of the day. ...

Almost all the world's cities have witnessed a construction boom geared towards the rich-and often alarmingly similar to one another-amidst a flood of poor migrants who have lost their land and gathered in the cities as a result of agriculture gaining an industrial and commercial character (Harvey, 2013: 52- 54).

In his work, Harvey has devoted considerable space to the development of the real estate market before and during the 2008 crisis. This is because the process of capital accumulation, which possesses a capitalist understanding, does not occur through surplus value alone. The real estate market also makes a significant contribution to this process. Ultimately, this process has also brought with it a crisis. This process detailed by Harvey is, in fact, nothing more than the attempt to ensure the absorption of capital accumulation through cities. However, the process also brought crisis with it. While capitalism causes problems such as income inequality, environmental pollution, disorderly city and regional development, and class differentiation, the crises that emerge with the construction boom make the problems of cities thoroughly intractable.

The solution to the problems created by the capitalist system can be facilitated by trying to ensure social justice in space. To achieve this, in capitalism, the state intervenes in social and economic life to correct distortions in income distribution, to eliminate inequalities within cities, between cities of various sizes, and between villages and cities, and to assign the social costs caused by individuals to those who create them. For this purpose, the state intervenes in city life with aims such as reorganizing central business districts, relocating low-income groups to areas with higher standards of settlement, preventing social conflicts arising from ethnic segregation, and ensuring that low-income families benefit equally not only from public services like health, education, and housing but also from the right to participate in the urban planning process (Davidoff, 1964; Frieden & Morris, 1968, as cited in Keleş, 1976). Along with all this, central and city governments, which are caught up in the construction boom today, must act by accepting that cities are living organisms, rather than seeing them as machines and tools for absorbing capital accumulation. Otherwise, cities will lose their identity and vitality and turn into piles of concrete.

In the context of the environment, Lenin stated on the subject that the capitalist mode of production and the competition specific to capitalism "destroy the productive forces of the earth" (as cited from 353 in Keleş, 1976). At this point, before directly blaming capitalism, it must be stated that there is literature on the existence of environmental problems in the pre-capitalist era as well.

Environmental problems also existed in the pre-industrial era. However, these problems never reached today's dimensions. Environmental problems, previously expressed in a regional context, have become globalized with capitalism (Foster, 2002). Consequently, capitalism is seen as the fundamental cause of the environmental crisis

and social inequalities (Tanuro, 2011). Additionally, industrialization, technological development, and development are seen as factors that damage the environment. However, it is not possible to speak of the negatives of modern industrial or mechanical development in the abstract. On the contrary, these developments make humanity freer. In contrast, in the capitalist system, industrialization causes unemployment where it should shorten working hours (Biolat, 1973: 118). Therefore, it would not be wrong to say that technology is a developmental element that accelerates capitalism.

Technology was born and disseminated in a historical period when capitalism was being restructured globally; this was not a coincidence; today's technological revolution was a tool of fundamental importance for capitalism. Therefore, the new society that emerged in this process of change, although it shows considerable historical diversity in different countries depending on their histories, cultures, institutions, and their specific relationships with global capitalism and information technology, is both capitalist and informational (Castells, 2005: 15).

Castells also interpreted technology as both capitalist and informational. According to him, the fact that the act of producing occurs through the application of knowledge upon knowledge is an informational move. This move, while being a mode of development, also globalizes capitalism (Castells, 2005: 23). However, the informational development that Castells emphasizes here does not create an informational development move in all countries of the world by globalizing capitalism.

The exploitative dimension of capitalism should not be forgotten. It is evident that the large main cities of third-world countries with underdeveloped economies feed the system through exploitative economic relations. Large metropolitan centers have established dominance over smaller ones (Harvey, 1973: 262). This state of dominance continues today. When technological developments are added to the situation, it is quite easy to prove, by researching the costs and prices of today's technological devices, that the countries and companies holding the technological development initiative achieve capital accumulation by creating surplus value through underdeveloped or developing countries via global capitalism. Despite all this, capitalism has been imposed upon the world as a modern and ideal system. Weber, in his work *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism*, summarizes the spirit of capitalism as follows:

No one knows who will live in that cage in the future, or whether at the end of this tremendous development entirely new prophets will arise, or there will be a great rebirth of old ideas and ideals, or, if neither, mechanized petrification, embellished with a sort of convulsive self-importance. For of the last stage of this cultural development, it might well be truly said: Specialists without spirit, sensualists without heart; this nullity imagines that it has attained a level of civilization never before achieved (Weber, 1997: 157).

In conclusion, while capitalism causes interregional inequality, social stratification, group conflicts, and income inequality in cities, it requires urbanization due to its need for exploitation. This is because it is only in this way that capitalism can transform the surplus value produced within its system. Furthermore, it is evident that with technological developments, capitalism has become entirely global. Capitalism continuously acquires new tools to perpetuate its system. At the same time, referencing another important period of urbanization, the idea prevails that modernism and postmodernism, in this context, are also tools that ensure the thorough expansion of capitalism in cities.

3.2. Modernism and Postmodernism City

The political, social, cultural, and economic elements of the West, its scientific and technological thought, and its philosophical structure, as a whole, constitute modernism (Lawrence, 2001: 19).

Although modernism has a very different history in the fields of art and literature, it is a term used for the entire mindset that accompanied the great social change spurred by the Industrial Revolution in the world. The movement, which began to make a name for itself in the fields of art, architecture, and literature from the second half of the nineteenth century onward, also named the dominant paradigm in at least the first half of the twentieth century (Aktay, 2008: 8).

When the literature on the emergence of modernism is examined, it is seen that there are studies searching for clues prior to the Renaissance and the Enlightenment Period. Of course, every form of thought has a period of seed-planting and development before it sprouts. Within the scope of this study, the social life dimension of modernism is at the forefront. Therefore, in this context, it is necessary to assign a timeline to modernism.

Modernism, as a model of social life, emerged with the Enlightenment Period (Keyman, 2000: 23). As Martinelli (2005) states, modernism has a positivist methodology and a rational point of view against the dogmatic understanding of religion and the scholastic mindset of the Middle Ages. The visibility of modernism particularly increased with the technical, social, and cultural changes experienced with the Industrial Revolution. Indeed, the natural abode of modernism, which is argued to be the art of cities, has been the cities themselves (Harvey, 2010). This should not be surprising. Because the technical, social, and cultural changes experienced with the Industrial Revolution were directly reflected in city life and also caused urbanization at an incredible speed. Accordingly, the reflection of modernism in cities has been through structures specific to its understanding, which even influenced the habits of society. Modernism refers to the contemporary. However, it does not stop there; it is an attempt to reject the old, and therefore, a demolition of the past.

The destruction of the social mechanisms that link the contemporary experience of the individual to that of earlier generations is one of the most characteristic and eerie phenomena of the late twentieth century. At the end of the century, most young men and women grew up in a sort of permanent present, lacking any organic relation to the past of the times they live in (Hobsbawm, 1996: 15).

According to Hobsbawm (1996), the most characteristic and eerie feature of the late 20th century is the destruction of the social mechanisms between the present day and previous generations. With the destruction of these mechanisms, the youth living at the end of the 20th century lived in a continuous present, as they were deprived of the organic bond between the time they were in and the past.

The severing of the present's bond with the past means the severing of the future's bond with the present in the next historical period. Therefore, in this situation, it becomes an expected state for people who lack an organic bond with a common past to become disconnected from their cultures, their civilizations, and the unifying elements of the city. For, as Karakaç states, "Civilization is based on the essence of culture. A society produces a culture. A civilization is born from that culture. A nation is born from that civilization. A state is born from that nation" (2012a: 19).

This multifaceted rupture will be directly reflected in the city and society. In fact, while wanting to build a more functional city, the city that is built devoid of the memory of history, language, and culture, consisting only of buildings, will lose its vitality due to this rupture. Indeed, as cited from Corbusier: Modernists, because they looked at the city functionally, also saw the city as factories that produce buildings (Ragon, 2010: 386).

Modern architecture has an understanding that favors structures of a height not built in previous periods, is identified with the use of open spaces, glass surfaces, iron, steel, and concrete materials, adopts simplicity in form, and, while being function-oriented, contains permanent and universal aesthetic values. According to Loos, who rejected the symbolic value of the structure, "ornament is a crime," and therefore, unadorned architecture, while fulfilling the function of the structure, must be made as economically as possible, at the lowest cost. In this way, the structure will appeal to society (Loos, 1998, as cited in Çelikkilek, 2017: 84). While modern architecture emphasizes cubic forms, geometric shapes, and Cartesian grids with the use of reinforced concrete, steel, and glass, it does not include ornamentation, stylistic motifs, traditional roofs, or decorative details (Bozdoğan, 2015).

In contrast to modern architecture's effort for glass, unadorned, simple, high, and "permanent and economical" structures, Baudelaire, in his work *The Painter of Modern Life*, expresses the modern as: "Modernity is the transient, the fleeting, the contingent" (Harvey, 2010: 23). The emphasis on the "moment" here refers to that which will lose its importance in the next period of time. If what exists now loses its value and becomes outdated in the next period, the fact that modernism speaks of economical structures seems quite contradictory. For what is built today, falling into the state of being "old" tomorrow, will give rise to the need to create the "new."

Additionally, although the desire to build functional buildings at a low cost sounds appealing, the emphasis on buildings of unprecedented height and structures where the outputs of capitalist production and predominantly specific materials are used raises the issue of questioning modernism in terms of each city's identity and its appropriateness for society. For, as Giddens states, modernity is globalizing by its very nature (Giddens, 2012: 156). However, for every city to have the same appearance and the presence of high, glass, or reinforced concrete structures in every city can cause the city to lose its meaning and identity. To give an example, high-rise and glass-intensive buildings, which are rarely encountered in Islamic Cities, have become a sign of

civilization as they spread globally under the name of modern. However, these structures are not suitable for the lifestyle of Islamic society, which prioritizes privacy, nor for the identity of Islamic Cities, which prioritize the mosque as the primary high-rise structure at first glance.

In contrast to this understanding, which is seen as a reflection of civilization, true civilization lies at the very core of Medina. What is referred to here is not the Medina of today, but the Medina where Islamic Civilization took root and spread from. The reason for this detail is that the city of Medina has also undergone socio-spatial change and transformation in the process leading up to the present day. Due to the influence of globalization, there are also structures there that conform to the modern understanding. The fact that Medina, which was not urbanized with architectural concerns, is today filled with piles of concrete, shows that global systems affect not only the cities but also the intellectual background of people. For the element that builds the city is the human being.

While today in almost all urban centers of the world, high-rise giant structures and clock towers are considered indicators of civilization, the prevailing view is that Medina, where the practice of true civilization took place, does not reflect its identity with giant structures and clock towers. Centuries ago, Ibn Khaldun, in his work, while distinguishing between the city dweller and the non-city dweller, emphasized that cities are places transformed by human hands.

The non-city dweller lives in an unspoiled nature and geographical environment untouched by human hands. Everything he sees, hears, touches, tastes, smells, eats, drinks, wears, inhabits, and uses is natural. It has not been altered by human hands to the point where its origin is unrecognizable, nor has it been forced into all sorts of different shapes (İbn-i Haldun, 1991: 872).

According to Haldun, the place where we can find the meanings of 'natural' as in untouched and unaltered, as mentioned in the quote, is not the city. In that case, does the city mean unnatural, altered by human hands to the point where its origin is unrecognizable? Considering today's modern cities, it is possible to answer yes to this question. For cities have now become similar to each other through the destruction of their unique values and nature. However, Karakoç stated that the Islamic City and the modern cities of the West differ from each other at the point of the destruction of nature: "...In Islamic Civilization, there is no destruction of nature. On the contrary, nature has been held as valuable" (Karakoç, 2012). Therefore, it is necessary to find an answer to the question, 'What, then, has changed for Islamic Civilization?'

In the literature, ideas have been put forward that modernism is contrary to nature. According to Rousseau, it is necessary to turn to untouched nature. For modernism and civilization are not suitable for human nature (Loo & Reijen, 2014). The existence of matters in cities that are contrary to human nature will, in turn, corrupt human nature and the city.

For, "The city, as the environment where morality, art, philosophy, and religious thought develop, is the medium in which man completes his duty in this world and the meaning of his existence at the highest level. In this consciousness, it also ensures the formation of the city's shape and becomes the foundation for man to reach his highest level of development" (Cansever, 2013: 19).

While the city has such a profound impact on people's lives, it is inevitable that the act of changing even a single structure, with buildings virtually turning into skyscrapers under a globalizing approach in the name of modernism, and changing the materials used in buildings (using more glass, or even making buildings entirely of glass)-matters that appear to belong to architecture-will in fact have an effect on the values that constitute a society's existence: morality, art, philosophy, religion, history, and culture.

To understand the effects of modernism's globalizing approach, it is useful to establish what globalization is. As expressed by Altıntaş and Pektaş, globalization,

can be described as an uncontrollable series of transformations that has made itself intensely felt since the 1980s, has different dimensions-primarily economic, political, and cultural-and, in parallel with developments in technology and communication, renders the concepts of time and space insignificant and is based on mutual dependency (2020: 119).

For Nietzsche, who proceeded from the idea that people and the inner world of modernism also have their chains with regard to the modernism imposed on cities and thus on all areas of life in a global context, Harvey (2010) stated the following: "...he was swimming in a sea of chaos, anarchy, destruction, individual alienation, and despair. Behind the facade of modern life, governed by knowledge and science, he had sensed the existence

of wild, primitive, and utterly ruthless life energies.” The view is that Harvey’s emphasis on “ruthless and wild” hypothetically refers to the imposition of Western culture, which came to the forefront after the Industrial Revolution, on all world countries under the name of modernism. As a result of this cultural imposition, a new society and order also emerge, of course. In fact, what is at issue here is the destruction of an existing social order.

The basic condition of modernism is creative destruction (Karakurt, 2006: 7). In fact, this destruction by modernism is so radical that it would claim even the belief in established habits is irretrievably lost (Sim, 2000: 22). Therefore, for modernism, which wants to build cities from scratch according to its own principles, Harvey’s expression “ruthless and wild” seems quite appropriate. For modernism is: “the emergence of a new type of society, characterized by complex processes in economic, political, and cultural change” (Swingewood, 1998: 9). When it is considered that the new society, which emerges as a homogeneous structure, will have no historical, cultural, or social ties, it is possible that modernization may actually bring about a sick society and a sick, pale urban.

According to Jacobs, modernism corrupts spaces, making them less humane. To revitalize and diversify cities and to ensure they possess wealth in an economic context, it is necessary to provide cities with low-rise buildings that have multi-purpose use and more than one function, in a mix of old and new buildings. Additionally, sufficient population density must be provided in these areas (from 1961, as cited in Bingöl, 2014: 17). However, what is understood from Smith’s definition of modernization is that the goal is not to revitalize cities or give them an identity. According to Smith, modernization first begins with modernism gaining a universal dimension, that is, with the process of social change, a stage which also includes the matter of religion’s decline. In the second stage, with the transition between the traditional and the modern, secularization and capitalism become visible. In the final stage, ideal modernization is achieved when developing countries implement modernization policies (Smith, 2011: 96). As can be understood, modernism has quite a variety of mechanisms of influence.

Modernism, which is Western-centric and affects the entire world on a global scale, should not be seen merely as industrialization. Its mechanisms of influence are: industrialization, increasing urbanization, advanced rationalization in thought and action, the decline of magic and religion, democratization, the reduction of social differences, and extreme individualism (Loo & Reijen, 2014: 14). Modernism also contains many contradictions within itself.

... Weber points out that while the process of rationalization frees the modern human from the prohibitions of magic and myths, it also simultaneously binds and cages him (which is a paradoxical situation). Here, we see the radical tension between the liberating and freedom-restricting aspects of the modernization process coming to the forefront (2014: 14).

The rationalization that comes with modernism is reflected in cities as a loss of identity, becoming monotonous and anonymous. When this situation became widespread in the 1950s, cities began to lose their original architecture and identities. Thereupon, the modern understanding, which had shunned ornament and color, tried to give cities an identity by coloring the walls and structures. The de-identification brought by modernism also kills the sense of belonging in society. For this de-identification created in the city will, in some way, permeate the urban society either before or after. The de-identification of society, just like cities losing their identity and becoming alienated from their essence, history, and culture, also alienates every individual in society from their core values.

The dimensions of alienation can be understood more clearly through the definition of identity. “In its simplest definition, identity is the sum of answers given by individuals, groups, societies, or communities to the question, ‘who are you, who are you from?’” (Güvenç, 2016: 3). Therefore, it is inevitable that societies that cannot produce and protect their own values will perish through “alienation,” the most ruthless form of exploitation (Öz, 2020: 100).

In summary, modernization organizes and shapes urban space according to the principles of capitalism. The city becomes the subject of all arrangements made in line with capitalism (Karakurt, 2006: 6).

... The tendency to facilitate the fluidity of capital and increase its accumulation brings with it new spatial arrangements, and old environments continuously enter a cycle of change. The fact that space undergoes a change in line with the requirements of the capitalist economy, bringing its quantitative

values to the forefront, and the loosening of its ties with its location and geography, presents itself as a phenomenon of space specific to modern times. The structure of spatial discontinuities is determined by capital; capital, using this feature of space, makes new arrangements and definitions that will increase its own profitability (2006: 6).

Therefore, due to all these effects of modernism on the city, it also affects and changes all areas that concern society.⁴ Therefore, its effects are destructive. Along with all this, when cities where the modern understanding is dominant take on a state of having no core values, being identity-less, lifeless, and colorless, postmodernism reflects a more colorful and highly differentiating understanding.

The promise of modernism was: to advance morality in society, to ensure justice in all social institutions, and to ensure people's happiness by leading the individual to understand themselves and the world. However, by the 20th century, it was understood that modernism had failed to fulfill its promise (Habermas, 1996: 45).

According to Onis, postmodernism is "the conservative regression of modernism within itself" (Anderson, 2009: 10). In contrast to this statement by Anderson, the prefix "post-" before modernism means after-modernism. What is understood is that there is a difference in meaning and application. In fact, postmodernism does not even have an agreed-upon characteristic.

Neo-Marxists like Harvey define postmodernism as a higher stage of the global spread and homogenization of capitalism, i.e., capital (Best & Kellner, 2016: 24). While Toynbee used postmodernism to express negativity and collapse (Özdemir, 2004: 312), Rozenberg approached postmodernism in the context of a new cultural formation. According to Şaylan, citing Champman and Rozenberg, postmodernism is the heir to the tradition of thought and inquiry, which is important in human development (2020: 11-288). According to the Güncel Türkçe Sözlük (Contemporary Turkish Dictionary): In its literary sense, postmodernism is "the name for various styles and trends that emerged in the second half of the 20th century after the modernist quest lost its vitality" (TDK, n.d.). In its architectural sense, postmodernism means: "the style in contemporary architecture that tends to freely use different structural forms, setting aside functionality" (TDK, n.d.). As can be understood from its architectural meaning, contrary to modernism, ornament and exaggeration are used in postmodernist structures.

In the literature, Champman, who used the word postmodern, used the term for paintings he saw as more modern and more avant-garde within the framework of the Impressionist painting movement, an art movement that emerged in France in the 1870s (Şaylan, 2020: 6). One of the most striking socio-spatial elements of the postmodern understanding in cities belongs to an apartment building in Spain. It belongs to the apartment named Walden 7, with exactly 446 units, built in Spain in 1975. The structure "...tries to provide a solution to problems of today's cities such as individualization, the disappearance of collective activities, and the loss of public spaces. Walden 7, which has a structure that contrasts with its external environment, proposes a society within itself" (Arkitektüel, 2018).

The postmodern understanding, like modernism, proposes a new social structure. And the structure mentioned above came to life in accordance with the high-rise building concept in modernism. The point being explained is that modernism and postmodernism have a great deal in common.

Although there are different thoughts about postmodernism, it should not be forgotten that postmodernism is a part of modernity. But a modern work can only be seen as modern as long as it is postmodern (Lyotard, 2013: 155-156). When looking at the surroundings of all postmodern structures, it is seen that they are buildings that are quite different from their environment and easily distinguishable from other structures. Studies must be conducted on the appropriateness of this distinguishability put forth by the postmodernist understanding for the life of the society and the identity of the city, and how the differentiation or colorfulness of socio-spatial urban elements that do not contain a piece of the history and cultural memory of the city's inhabitants will affect the bond between society and the city.

Considering that postmodernity disempowers and negates the individual (Esgin, 2008: 471-472), the argument prevails that the differentiation of socio-spatial elements in cities by the postmodern understanding, independent of the values of the society and the city, actually alienates the individual from society and the city, therefore disempowering and negating the individual.

⁴ "The structure of modernity (with its institutions, its daily way of life, its cognitive and normative themes, and what have you) appears to the individual as a necessarily alien, powerful, and essentially coercive force that upends one's own life and the lives of other individuals for whom one is responsible." (Berger & Keller, 1985: 135).

The modern and postmodern understandings find life through the destruction of the past by constantly referring to the present. It is clear that this situation will de-identify and alienate cities and society. Therefore, studies to be conducted on the unique values of cities and civilizations, without excluding modern influences, gain importance in order to prevent alienation, de-identification, and the destruction of the past.

4. BASIC PRINCIPLES OF THE ISLAMIC CITY CONCEPTION

Cities emerged and developed first in Mesopotamia and then in other places along with the Agricultural Revolution. Similarly, the beginning of humanity's adventure of civilization is also based on the agricultural revolution. Therefore, there is an overlap between the concepts of city and civilization, both terminologically (Medina/medeniyet) and in terms of historical process. However, it is seen that this overlap is not taken into account in studies on the history of cities and civilizations written independently of each other. The failure to adequately study the prophets, the civilizations they founded, and their cities is a fundamental deficiency that is also conspicuous today (Taşçı, 2017: 48). In this context, it is quite essential to set forth the fundamental principles and function of the Islamic City concept.

It should not be forgotten that the city is the place where people, whose basic needs have been met, can produce surplus value by using their minds, talents, and freedoms. This is precisely a journey of discovery into one's own existence and meaning. Where knowledge prevails over ignorance, rational reasoning and deliberation over violence, refinement and grace over crudeness and crowds, and quality over mediocrity, it means that city life is performing its true function (Mumford, 1987; Kalın, 2019: 239). Therefore, the necessity also arises to present all aspects of Islamic Cities, which allow city life to perform its true function.

As explained in the Holy Qur'an: "But Satan caused them to slip out from there and removed them from where they were. And We said, 'Go down, as enemies to one another, and you will have upon the earth a place of settlement and provision for a time'" (Kur'an Yolu Meali, (Date of Access: 27.09.2020), al-Baqarah 2/36).

Based on the verse, the thesis emerges that Prophet Adam, as the first human on earth, played a role in the founding of the first city or cities. For the emergence of cities, in the history of cities, is based on the beginning of settled life and trade corresponding to agricultural production. The place where this depiction occurred is Mesopotamia, that is, the places where the prophets accepted in the Holy Qur'an lived (Taşçı, 2017: 56).

Additionally, as is often mentioned in the history of the city, if we are to diagnose the city, we must travel from the best-known city structures and functions back to their earliest elements, deeper and further back, no matter how distant in time, space, and culture from the first excavated layer of the mound. Before the city, there were hamlets, sacred places, and villages. Before the village, there were nomadic camps, primitive shelters, caves, and marker stones. Before all these, there was the tendency for social life, which humankind clearly shared with many other animal species (Mumford, 2007: 15). The point here is that there were smaller settlements before cities. Topçu's explanation, which opposes this, is as follows:

... it was thought that before forming society, people lived in a scattered state. J.J. Rousseau accepts that the first humans lived in herds. Sociology, however, has revealed the truth that humans have never lived alone..., that they have lived in societies since the primitive era. ... Researches conducted among the primitive people living in the middle of Australia have revealed that community life, not individual existence, is the primitive state. From the result of researches conducted on the first societies, we obtain a truth regarding the spiritual nature of the individual. That is, the instinct to live in a society is present in human creation. While living in a society is a necessity connected to human creation, there are also some other influences that drive humans to live in society. These influences are the impulses of the physiological structure, climatic conditions, and with the satisfaction of needs, the necessity of mutual protection from enemy attacks and the necessity of performing religious rites together (2001: 20).⁵

Similar to this statement by Topçu, Taşçı, by referencing Klaus Schmidt's words "first came the temple, then the city" from the Göbeklitepe excavations near Urfa, states that cities could have existed before the development of agriculture, contrary to the accepted view (2017: 55). Similarly, Taşçı, while stating that the

⁵ A counterpart to the necessity of performing religious rites together, one of the necessities of living in a society as expressed by Topçu, could be the following: "Indeed, the first House [of worship] established for mankind was that at Makkah-blessed and a guidance for the worlds" (Kur'an Yolu Meali, Al-i Imran 3/96). The house mentioned here is the Kaaba.

first city was founded by Prophet Adam and his children, draws attention to the 7th verse of Surah Ash-Shura (2017: 57): “And thus We have revealed to you an Arabic Qur’an that you may warn the Mother of Cities [Makkah] and those around it and warn of the Day of Assembly, about which there is no doubt. A party will be in Paradise and a party in the Blaze” (Elmalılı Hamdi Yazır Meali (Date of Access: 03.01.2022), ash-Shura 42/7). He states that Mecca, referred to as the Mother of Cities, as mentioned in the verse as Bekke, means “crowded place,” thus expressing that the first city, Mecca, was not a place where a few people lived, but a crowded city. Consequently, it is possible to say that the human adventure that began with Prophet Adam evolved towards city life from the very beginning, and with the coming together of all elements, the city emerged structurally (2017: 57).

Furthermore, with reference to the study where the adherents of Islam, that is, the Muslim world-in other words, the giant network of cities stretching from India to the West, through which the flow of all kinds of products, branches of knowledge, ideas, and cultures took place by land and sea-is described (Serjeant, 1997: 15), it would not be wrong to say that Islam is a religion of the city, as has been stated in previous sections.

Up to this part of the study, it has been touched upon that the history of the city, and consequently the sources of the city, have been expressed from Western sources and that there are some contradictions in these matters. The necessity of addressing these contradictions arises entirely from the desire to clearly present the Islamic City. The issue to be addressed after this section is the fundamental principles of the Islamic City concept and the functions of the Islamic City, a part of which was actually attempted to be set forth above. First, it must be stated that civilization, a concept upon which the Islamic City is rooted, consists of three structures: Ahkâm (divine rulings), a society that adheres to fiqh (Islamic jurisprudence), and the city (Bergen, 2020: 16). It would not be wrong to say that the foundation of the Islamic City concept is based on the Muslim community. For the Muslim community holds an important place in the understanding of Islam regarding matters of worship and the order of city life.

“You are the best nation produced [as an example] for mankind. You enjoin what is right and forbid what is wrong and believe in Allah. If only the People of the Scripture had believed, it would have been better for them. Among them are believers, but most of them are defiantly disobedient” (Kur’an Yolu Meali, (Date of Access: 07.01.2022), Al-i Imran 3/110).

The Muslim community has been given the good tidings of being the best nation, but it is advised not to repeat the sins mentioned in the verses of the Holy Qur’an where it is narrated that people and cities incurred divine wrath:

“And Allah presents an example: a city which was safe and secure, its provision coming to it in abundance from every location, but it denied the favors of Allah. So Allah made it taste the envelopment of hunger and fear for what they had been doing” (Kur’an Yolu Meali, (Date of Access: 19.10.2021), an-Nahl 16/112).

“And there had certainly come to them a Messenger from among themselves, but they denied him; so punishment seized them while they were wrongdoers” (an-Nahl 16/113).

The Prophet of Islam, Muhammad, also informs of the importance of the Muslim community (congregation) in the following hadiths: “A believer to another believer is like a building whose different parts enforce each other” (Bukhari, Adab, 27, as cited in Keleş, DİB). “The believers in their mutual kindness, compassion and sympathy are just like one body. When one of the organs suffers, the whole body responds to it with wakefulness and fever.” (Bukhari, Adab, 36; Tecrid-i Sarih, 12-134, as cited in Keleş, DİB). Here, the values that Islamic society attaches importance to in solidarity and social organization are set forth. In the given context, Lapidus explains the social organization in the Islamic City model in four levels. These levels are: the State Organization, Religious Communities (the inter-sectarian organization of society), Artisan ahi organizations (Guilds), and neighborhoods. However, Lapidus, who sees the neighborhood as the most important model of social organization, also emphasizes that these places are centers of strong social control and social solidarity (Sjoberg, 1960: 190-222; Lapidus, 1984: 49-52). In the Islamic City, there are no social strata in the physical structure of the neighborhood. In this respect, spatial proximity in terms of class solidarity is not a rule or a requirement in any of the neighborhoods within the city’s physical structure. The rich and the poor can live side by side in the neighborhoods (Aktüre, 1978). It is thought that this togetherness is ensured by the socio-spatial element of the mosque. For, it does not seem possible for there to be an economy-based stratification among those who worship in the same socio-spatial element, prostrate together, and then establish a method of

commerce in the marketplace with an egalitarian understanding far from competition. Indeed, in the Islamic understanding, everything is connected with a delicate balance.

To give an example: Islamic jurisprudence (fiqh) constructs the Islamic City that will bring forth the mosque-market-mu'akhat (brotherhood) society. The obligation for men to give a dower (mahr) to women has compelled men to engage in trade. In this context, the Friday prayer is an economic gathering. Because of this prayer, people who are brothers cannot establish a competitive market with each other. On the other hand, as a social duty, the principles cannot be violated due to the duty of establishing a family/society (Bergen, 2020: 16).

In conclusion, the importance of the Muslim community, which is at the foundation of the Islamic City concept, is also present in the verses of the Holy Qur'an. Additionally, it can be said that the social organization of the Islamic City consists of neighborhoods, guilds, the state organization, and religious communities, but that the economic dimension of the social organization is not reflected in neighborhood life as stratification

5. COMPARATIVE EVALUATION

Within the scope of this study, the fundamental differences between the Islamic city concept and modern urbanism models become evident along the axes of origin, philosophy, socio-economic structure, architecture, and the relationship established with nature. The fundamental contrasts between these two paradigms, which were detailed in the previous sections of the text, can be summarized as follows:

Origin:

The origin of the Western urban form lies in the capitalist economic system, which takes the profit motive as its fundamental guide (Keleş, 1976). This structure is the most concrete example of the Gesellschaft (society) type conceptualized by Ferdinand Tönnies, one of the classic names in sociology. Gesellschaft defines a structure where individuals form impersonal, rational, and interest-oriented relationships (Tönnies, 1987). The urban form, in this framework, becomes a rational 'machine' (Ragon, 2010: 386) and a tool for capital accumulation. As Wirth emphasized, the size, density, and heterogeneity of the urban sphere lead to the superficiality of social relations, the anonymity of the individual, and the dominance of an instrumental mentality (Wirth, 1938). The principle of 'creative destruction' (Karakurt, 2006: 7) of modernism becomes the philosophical legitimizer of this process that severs these historical and social ties.

In contrast, the Islamic city derives its ontology from the concept of 'civilization' (medeniyet) (Bergen, 2020: 16) and from a foundation close to the spirit of Gemeinschaft, Tönnies's other concept. The idealized form of this model is a spatial manifestation of the Ummah (community of believers) understanding, where individuals are bound to one another by common beliefs, traditions, and mutual responsibilities. The city is not merely a settlement but also an 'organism' where the social and worship practices of Islam are lived, and a moral and spiritual order is preserved (Cansever, 2013: 19). Nezar AlSayyad states that the central placement of the Friday Mosque (Masjid-i Juma) and the ruler's palace (Dar al-Imara) in the founding of early Islamic cities shows that the city was designed not only as an administrative center but also as a religious and social one (AlSayyad, 1991).

Socio-Spatial Order:

The capitalist urban form reproduces and reinforces class differences in space (Chapin, 1965: 10-21). The "concentric zones" theory of the Chicago School reveals how social status transforms into a rigid spatial hierarchy in the modern industrial urban center (Burgess, 1925). Harvey, in more critical terms, defines this situation as capital shaping the urban sphere in its own interests and, in this process, the expropriation of the "right to the city" from the lower classes (Harvey, 1973).

In the Islamic city, however, in its idealized structure, the neighborhood (mahalle) stands out as a unit of solidarity where the rich and poor live together (Aktüre, 1978). One of the most important mechanisms that provides this social integration is the waqf (pious foundation) system. Waqfs, by financing public services such as mosques, madrasas, hospitals (darüşşifa), and fountains (sebil), ensured that urban services reached the entire community without class distinction and became a spatial guarantee of social justice (Lapidus, 1984). Nevertheless, Abu-Lughod emphasizes that the 'Islamic city' model did experience segregation based on ethnic, sectarian, or occupational groupings, but she stresses that this was based on a different logic than modern capitalist segregation (Abu-Lughod, 1987).

Architectural Identity

The modernist architectural principle that ‘ornament is a crime’ (from Loos, 1998, as cited in Çelikkbilek, 2017: 84) and its universalist claim have created identical, identity-less urban forms that ignore local climate, culture, and materials. Jacobs harshly criticized this abstract and imposing approach of modernist urban planning; in its place, she advocated for an organic, complex, lived, and human-scale urban fabric (Jacobs, 1961).

Islamic city architecture, in contrast, exhibits a pragmatism deeply rooted in local conditions and social values. Inward-facing courtyard houses provide privacy, while narrow, winding streets create shade in hot climates, making public space more livable. In this civilization, “there is no destruction of nature. On the contrary, nature has been held as valuable” (Karakoç, 2012). Architecture aims to establish a life in harmony with nature rather than dominating it.

While the Western urban model offers a potentially alienating space shaped by the logic of rationalization, individualization, and capital, the Islamic city paradigm represents a holistic alternative built upon the ideals of community (cemaat-the Muslim community, which should not be understood as a different form of sectarianism), spirituality, and social justice. Although academic literature offers important warnings that this ideal was not always fully met in historical reality, the comparison between these two models continues to be an extremely fertile intellectual tool for understanding the problems of contemporary urban centers and for designing more just, sustainable, and humane living environments.

6. CONCLUSION

The evaluations made throughout this study have revealed that the distinction between the modern Western urban form and the traditional Islamic city is not merely one of architectural style or geographical difference, but rather represents two radically different paradigms regarding existence, society, and space. On one hand, there is an “urban” model that capital and the rational mind operate like a mechanical cog, shaping the human and society in line with its own purposes. On the other hand, there is a “city” ideal, at whose center lies the spiritual and worldly integrity of the human being, where space serves a divine order and a moral purpose, and which is envisioned as a living organism.

The analyses show that the capitalist and modernist urban model pays the price for its promised progress and prosperity with a heavy ontological void. This model-fragmented by class divisions, de-identified by severing its ties with the past, and destructive of nature by viewing it as a commodity-has brought contemporary humanity to the brink of a crisis of belonging and meaning. Cities, as Weber (1997) pointed out, have virtually transformed into a manifestation woven from concrete and steel; the individual, within these giant structures, has become alienated from their fellow beings and from their own essence.

In contrast to this pessimistic picture, the Islamic city has been presented throughout this study as a refuge and a normative alternative. This model-where the spirit of community, solidarity, privacy, and the human scale are preserved; where the market is balanced by the mosque, commerce by justice, and architecture by humility-stands out as a space of memory that contains the values lost by the modern world.

However, it is essential to open a discussion at this point: To what extent does the Islamic city model presented in this study reflect the full complexity of historical reality? Undoubtedly, this is an ‘ideal-type’ analysis. As Abu-Lughod (1987) also warned, it can be misleading to see historical Islamic cities as utopias, free from all conflict, power struggles, and social stratification. These cities also had their own internal tensions and flaws. Therefore, the value of this model lies not in its having been applied ‘flawlessly’ in history, but in the critical potential that its founding principles and intent offer to the present day. The goal is not to blindly imitate the past, but to rediscover the wisdom that lies in the spirit of that past and has not lost its meaning today.

In this context, future studies, moving beyond this ideal-type analysis, can empirically examine how contemporary cities in the Islamic world, under the pressure of globalization and modernism, are in negotiation with these principles. What are the points where the traditional fabric resists, transforms, or disappears? Can modern technologies and planning approaches form a hybrid model with the values of the Islamic city?

Ultimately, this study claims that the issue is not a simple “East-West” or “tradition-modernity” opposition, but that the real problem is knotted in the answers given to the questions, “what kind of city?” and “what kind of society?”. For whom and for what cities are built is the most fundamental decision regarding the future of civilization. For the ultimate purpose of a city is not to accumulate capital or piles of concrete, but to lay the groundwork for human beings to lead a meaningful and virtuous life.

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